

STUDY OF NEEDS IN DEVELOPING AN EXCELLENT CURRICULUM WITH PROJECT-BASED LEARNING FOR LEARNING MANAGEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS AT A PRIVATE ISLAMIC SCHOOL IN YALA PROVINCE, THAILAND

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Abstract

This research aims to study the need for developing an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for the learning management of secondary school students at a private Islamic school in Yala Province. Teachers who participated in the study to determine the need for developing an excellent curriculum with project-based learning found that the average score was at a high level, both in the actual context and in what it should be. On the other hand, when asking students for information, their decision to continue their education at the high school level, and the desired characteristics of students who graduate according to the 2008 core curriculum, revised in 2017, the average score of students who answered the questionnaire under existing conditions was at a medium to low level. However, the intended score should be at a high level.

Keywords: Study of Essential Needs, Curriculum Development, Project-Based Learning, Private Islamic Schools.

INTRODUCTION

Education is important in developing a country. Promoting education through teaching and learning in science and technology has been continuously promoted within the strategic and policy framework of the country under the operations of the Ministry of Education. The Ministry of Higher Education, Science, Research, and Innovation has tried to push and develop the quality of life through the education system so that students can have a better quality of life. The Ministry of Education has realized the importance of science, mathematics, and technology, so a policy has been established by the Basic Education Commission for educational institutions to open special classrooms focusing on science, mathematics, technology, etc. The request to open a particular classroom in the Educational Service Area Office was approved by the committee. Developing an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for private Islamic schools in the three southern border provinces. With the

cooperation of administrators in educational institutions, it is highly possible. Academics in the three southern border provinces and opinions of the community in the local context. This curriculum focuses on teaching and learning that promotes the potential of students with exceptional abilities in academics. Opportunities to compete at the national and international levels in the future can be created Personnel focused on the engineering group and future health groups can be produced by those who have the potential to research, invent, and develop innovations or new technologies under a project-based learning base. Therefore, for this research, the necessary need to develop a curriculum for Excellent project-based learning for private is of interest to us. Opportunities to compete at the national and international levels in the future can be created. Personnel focused on the engineering group can be produced by those who have the potential to research, invent, and develop innovations or new technologies under a project-based learning base.

Therefore, in the objective of this research, the necessary need to develop an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for private Islamic schools is being studied. Yala Province, Thailand, is a starting point for upgrading and transforming educational management in the 21st decade towards developing a curriculum for solving the above problems by establishing special classrooms (EPBL) to encourage students to complete their education at the lower secondary level. Continuing my high school studies in science and mathematics is of interest to me. This is under the project "Establishing Excellent Project Base Learning: EPBL classrooms in schools in the target areas of Yala Province"

THEORY AND RELATED RESEARCH

The concept of needs assessment is understood as follows: Needs are defined as things that need to be met or fulfilled, according to the dictionary and the viewpoint of educators, as stated by Stufflebeam et al. Categorizing needs according to 4 different perspectives.

- The discrepancy view addresses the difference between the desired action or performance and the observed action or observed performance.
- The democratic view is necessary to address the wishes or needs of most people who are considered a reliable reference group.
- The analytical view describes information about something in the organization that competent personnel have considered and concluded to be important to the agency and will cause development in the agency.
- The diagnostic view mentions the necessary need. Something that a person has determined to be defective or missing (deficiency or absence) can prove that the missing thing will cause damage to the organization.

Rumahlatu and Sangur (2019) the meaning of needs assessment is that it is a systematic process for arranging priorities, deciding on action plans, and managing resources. Becerra-Posada, et al. (2022).

The meaning of needs assessment is that it is a formal process that determines the gaps between current outputs or outcomes and desired outputs or outcomes and places these gaps in order of importance, selecting what is considered most important to solve of problem. The need assessment for curriculum development and teaching was studied.

It was found that education is a tool for developing students to become quality individuals, leading to a quality society. In an undesirable society, the use of inappropriate educational techniques or methods may reflect failures that occur. These failures may not be due to inappropriate methods, but rather to a lack of knowledge about the goals to be achieved through education. This leads to the use of inappropriate methods, guidelines, and resources, preventing the desired outcomes from being achieved.

Therefore, the methods and resources used in operations (Methods and Means) have a relationship that affects the outcomes that occur (Ends). Solving educational problems must be done in the process of organizing education. For this reason, needs assessment is necessary to be involved in the planning and development of education, assessing the necessary needs, and developing more knowledge.

From the period 1930 to 1950, a needs assessment was conducted to set goals for student development or career goals. During the period 1960-1970, a needs assessment was necessary for planning, determining the direction of development, and setting goals. In the period 1980 to the present, needs assessment is needed for planning and implementation.

Therefore, needs assessment prioritizes what is necessary and is integrated into every step of the curriculum development and teaching process to achieve the desired outcomes. (Lin, et al., 2021; Sirisrimangkorn, 2021; Hsu and Liao, 2022)

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Population

The research divided the population into 2 groups: teachers at private Islamic schools. In the area of Yala Province, there are 1,878 people and lower secondary school students. In the Yala Province area, for the academic year 2022, there are 14,341 people, as shown in Table 1 from Yala Provincial Private Education Office 2021.

Sample Group and Sample Selection

The research sample is divided into 2 sample groups

- A simple random sampling method was used by teachers. The key informants in this research were teachers, heads of science learning groups, or science teachers at private Islamic schools. In the area of Yala province under the Yala Provincial Private Education Office, there is one person per school, totaling 41 people.

The student is a junior high school student. Private Islamic school in the area of Yala Province, academic year 2022, under the Office of Private Education.

Which uses a multi-stage sampling method (Multi-stage Random Sampling) with the following steps:

The sample size is determined according to Yamane's method at a confidence level of not less than 95%, an error not more than 5%, totaling 14,341 people, using the following formula.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2} \quad (1)$$

$$n = \frac{14,341}{1 + 14,341(0.05)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$n \approx 389$$

Where n is the sample size (people)

N is the size of the population (people)

e is the sampling error equal to 0.05

Therefore, this research will have a sample size of 389 people.

Table 1: Number of Junior High School Students in Private Islamic School in Yala Province, Thailand. From Private Education Office, Yala Province, Thailand. (2021)

No.	School	Number of Teachers (people)	Number of students according to school size (people)		
			Small	Medium	Large
	Muang Yala				
1	Thamwittaya Foundation School	359			3,442
2	Satri Islamwittaya Foundation School	75		691	
3	Phatthanawittaya School	119		905	
4	Islamic Development School	41	128		
5	Suldin Wittaya Volunteer School	53	371		
6	Muslim Studies School	24	174		
7	Islamiyah School	29	397		
8	Udomsat Wittaya School	46	379		
9	Tarbia Tulwatan Foundation School	66		868	
10	Prateepwittaya School	29	122		
11	Prasarnwit Islamic School	17	83		
12	Darul Ulom Nibongbaru School	50	223		
13	Islahudin Wittaya School	32	254		
	Bannang Sata District				
14	Bible Witthaya School	71		515	
15	Charoensatwittaya School	21	173		
16	Damrongwittaya School	32	207		
17	Phadungsilwittaya School	15	114		
18	Alfallah Al Islami School	19	381		
19	Alawiya Wittaya School	86	171		
20	Bajao Wittaya Islamic School	52	314		
	Betong District				
21	Khairiya Wittaya Foundation School	19	279		
22	Maahad Darussalam School	13	147		

No.	School	Number of Teachers (people)	Number of students according to school size (people)		
			Small	Medium	Large
	Raman District				
23	Darul Hudah Wittaya School	95	82		
24	Phatthana Wittaya School	29	130		
25	Srifaridabaru Wittaya School	76	363		
26	Maahad Islamiyah School	81	309		
27	Mahaddawah Islamiyah School	14	68		
28	Pattanasat Wittaya School, Kota Bharu	19	166		
29	Saengthamwittaya School	7	62		
30	Saeng Ethics Wittaya School	20	215		
31	Bamrungsatwittaya School	7	97		
	Yaha District				
32	Suksawat Wittaya School	42	284		
33	Muslim Bamrung School	12	183		
34	Pratheep Thamwittaya School	22	351		
35	Darul Aitham Walmasakin School	14	133		
36	Dhamma Islam Suksa School	36	279		
37	Darawit School	19	224		
38	Islamic Wittaya School	22	99		
39	Somboonsart School	36	329		
40	Satri Sathanupatham School	13	161		
	Than To District				
41	Suthisat Wittaya School	46	468		
	Total	1,878	7,920	2,979	3,442

The sample was divided into three groups' small schools, medium schools, and large schools according to the proportion of the population of each school size. Sample groups with different characteristics were obtained. Then, a complete sample was obtained by calculating the sample size from the three school sizes according to the population proportion and the specified criteria.

$$n_i = \frac{N_i}{N/n} \quad (3)$$

Where n_i = sample size in stratum i

n = sample size

N_i = size of population in stratum i

N = population size

Private Islamic School in Yala Province, there were 41 schools, which can be divided into small, medium, and large schools. The number of samples in the schools each can be calculated as follows.

A sample of small schools would be $7,920 / (14,341/389) = 215$ students.

A sample of medium-sized schools would have $2,979 / (14,341/389) = 81$ students.

An example of a large school would be $3,442 / (14,341/389) = 93$ students.

Therefore, the sample will be 215 students from small schools, 81 from medium schools, and 93 from large schools.

Data Collection

The research process was divided into three steps by the researcher:

Step 1: The study of related documents and research, and

Step 2: The assessment of needs needed to develop an excellent curriculum with learning methods. The project serves as a base for private Islamic schools. In the area of Yala Province,

Step 3: Analysis of the causes of the need and determination of guidelines for developing an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for private Islamic schools.

In the area of Yala province, the details of data collection in this research are as follows: The quality of tools being created and checked the questionnaire and interview form were created by the researcher with the following steps:

- 1) Concepts, theories, and research related to the concept of needs assessment and project-based learning management were studied. Then, the conceptual framework used in the research was defined and definitions were established to be used as guidelines in creating the questionnaire. The content was covered according to the set objectives.
- 2) Two questionnaires were created, and classified according to target groups: teachers and students. Private Islamic school in the area of Yala province.
- 3) The created questionnaire was taken to 3 experts to check its content validity (Content Validity) by considering whether the questions were consistent with the objectives that needed to be studied. The consistency of the questions with the definitions of specific terms in each area was also assessed. The Content validity for scale/average (S-CVI/Ave) technique was used to find the average of the index to measure the consistency of the measuring instrument. The value that can be calculated is derived from the Item Content Validity Index (I-CVI) value for each question, calculated from the sum of the I-CVI value divided by the number of questions. A CVI value of not less than 0.80 is expected for a quality research instrument, and improvements are made according to the recommendations of experts.
- 4) The questionnaire was taken and tried out with ten teachers who were not the actual sample and 30 middle school students who were not the actual sample to find out the quality of the tool.

Moreover, it is used to determine the reliability or reliability of the questionnaire (Reliability) by calculating Cronbach Alpha-coefficients to check if respondents understand the questions by the objectives they want to study or not. Along with improving errors so that they can be used to collect actual data in the future. (Aminatun, et al., 2022; Lavonen, et al., 2022)

Collection of data from questionnaires the following steps were followed by the researcher for data collection. Preparation before collecting data a letter was written by the researcher to the Dean of the Faculty of Science, Technology, and Agriculture at Yala Rajabhat University to request permission from students and teachers who teach in the aforementioned educational institutions to provide information for research. The letter also included a request for permission to collect data for research. The date, time, and place for data collection must be arranged with the school. The letter was issued to the educational director of a private Islamic school in Yala province, under the Office of Private Education. In delivering and collecting questionnaires, the questionnaire was conducted by the researcher himself. The school director was requested to compile the questionnaires for the researcher on the specified date and time. Upon receiving the questionnaire, the accuracy of the information obtained will be checked by the researcher. Then, it will be used to analyze the results further. (Alotaibi, 2020; Cordova, Lahey, and Taghiyeva, 2023)

The Data from the Questionnaire was analyzed as follows

Information about the general status of respondents was analyzed using frequency distribution (f), percentage (%), mean (\bar{X}), and standard deviation (S.D). Data on needs in developing an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for private Islamic schools in the area of Yala province were analyzed by mean (\bar{X}) and standard deviation (S.D), which had performance levels based on the interpretation criteria as follows. The results of evaluating the current conditions and the conditions that should be in developing an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for private Islamic schools in the area of Yala Province refer to the average of 4.50 – 5.00. The highest level is indicated. The results of evaluating the current conditions and the conditions that should be in developing an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for private Islamic schools in the area of Yala Province refer to the average of 3.50 – 4.49. The level is high. The results of evaluating the current conditions and the conditions that should be in developing an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for private Islamic schools in the area of Yala Province refer to the average of 2.50 – 3.49. The level is moderate. The results of evaluating the status quo and the status quo in developing an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for private Islamic schools in the area of Yala Province refer to the average of 1.50 – 2.49. The level is low. The results of evaluating the current conditions and the conditions that should be used in developing an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for private Islamic schools in the area of Yala Province refer to the average value of 1.00 – 1.49. The lowest level is indicated.

Prioritize Essential Needs based on PNI_{modified} Index Values

Necessary needs are considered by considering the PNI modified index value of 0.3 or higher to be considered essential needs. Requirements are prioritized using a descending index. Higher-value indices have higher needs for development than lower-value indices. The side with the highest PNI modified index value will be the side with the most necessary needs, which is ranked number 1. The side with the PNI modified index value, followed by the side with the most necessary needs, is ranked number 2, and the side with the highest value, the least PNI modified index is the aspect with the slightest need, i.e., the last. (Perrault, and Albert,

2018; Kiong, et al., 2022)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The study results show the need to develop an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for the learning management of secondary school students at a private Islamic school in Yala Province.

Results of the study of needs in developing an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for learning management of secondary school students at private Islamic schools in Yala Province. A comprehensive investigation was conducted into the requirements and necessity for the development of an outstanding curriculum incorporating project-based learning, to manage the learning of secondary school students at a private Islamic school in Yala Province. The research established that an analysis of the average scores of the necessities essential for framing a superior curriculum with project-based learning was significant for managing the learning of secondary school students at private Islamic schools in Yala Province. The process involved testing and soliciting information from teachers regarding the desired attributes of graduates. This involved obtaining details about projects/activities that would make the curriculum outstanding, with a focus on project-based learning for the high school level. Students were also consulted to ascertain their willingness to continue their education at the high school level, with the information gathered on the desired characteristics of students graduating as per the 2008 core curriculum, revised in 2017. The analysis of the needs essential for the development of a superior curriculum, incorporating project-based learning for managing secondary school students' learning at a private Islamic school in Yala Province was noted in the results of the study pertaining to teachers. This research study involved the analysis of data. The collected data was derived from a sample of teachers in the southern border provinces, selected through a simple random sampling method (Simple random sampling). The primary informants in this study were the science subject teachers or science teachers from private Islamic schools in the Yala province, overseen by the Yala Provincial Private Education Office, with one representative per school, totaling 41 individuals. The research discovered that, of the teachers who responded to the questionnaire, 14 were males, comprising 34.1 percent, and 27 were females, making up 65.8 percent. The majority of the teachers originated from large schools, 20 individuals accounting for 48.8 percent, medium-sized schools were represented by 12 people, comprising 29.3 percent, and small schools were represented by nine individuals, accounting for 21.9 percent. The Thamwittaya Foundation School in Yala Province had the highest representation of 15 people, contributing to 36.6 percent of the total, as indicated in the data in Table 4.1. The majority of teachers who responded to the questionnaire had similar teaching experiences in science subjects, with no significant differences ($P > 0.05$), as shown in Table 2

Table 2: The Questionnaire in Each Private Islamic School in Yala Province was responded to by a Percentage of Teachers

School	Number of teachers (people)	Number of teachers (people) percentage
Udomsat Wittaya School	3	7.3
Tarbia Tulwantan Foundation School	5	12.2
Thamwittaya Foundation School	15	36.6
Phatthanawittaya School	6	14.6
Islamic Development School	3	7.3
Srifaridabaru Wittaya School	3	7.3
Suldin Wittaya Volunteer School	3	7.3
Islamiyah School	3	7.3

Table 3: The Percentage of Science Teaching Experience of Teachers at Private Islamic Schools in Yala Province was recorded

School	Number of teachers (people)	Number of teachers (people) percentage
1-5 Years	13	31.7
5-10 Years	14	34.1
>10 Years	14	34.1

The desired characteristics of students who graduated with education in morality, ethics, knowledge, and intellectual skills are included in the analysis of the average scores of the needs for the development of an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for managing the learning of secondary school students at a private Islamic school in Yala Province for teachers. Numerical analysis skills, communication, and use of information technology, as well as activities to develop an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for the high school level, are included. As shown in Table 4.3, it was found that the average scores for morality and ethics were at a high level in all criteria. But the condition should be respecting rights and listening to the opinions of others, including respect for the value and dignity of humanity, and respecting the rules and regulations of organizations and society. The result is in a very high range, with mean values of 4.54 ± 0.50 and 4.73 ± 0.50 , respectively.

A study of needs in developing an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for learning management of secondary school students at a private Islamic school in Yala Province was conducted. 41 teachers and 389 students, all of whom were from the Yala province, were questioned. The data regarding the traits they wanted their graduating students to have was questioned by the teachers, along with information about projects and activities to develop an excellent curriculum with project-based learning. For high school students, asking for information about students' decisions to continue their education at the high school level was combined with information on the desired characteristics of students who graduate according to the 2008 core curriculum, revised in 2017. The results of the study are summarized as follows: The need for the development of an excellence curriculum with project-based learning for the learning management of secondary school students in private Islamic schools in Yala Province was indicated by the results of the study. The average score obtained from asking

teachers in a study of the needs needed to develop an excellent curriculum with project-based learning was high in both the actual context and the expected condition. But, on the other hand, when inquiring about students' information, it was found that the average score of students who answered the questionnaire about actual conditions would be at a moderate to low level, despite the condition should be at a high level.

The Results of the Study required the Development of a Project-Based Curriculum of Excellence for Islamic Private Secondary School Students. Yala Province for Students

A project-based curriculum of excellence for Islamic private secondary school students was required to be developed based on the results of the study. In this study, the data were analyzed in this research, and data from a sample of students in the southern border provinces was collected by sampling junior high school students at Private Islamic School in Yala Province, Academic Year 2565. It was affiliated with the Office of Private Education, which used a multi-step sampling method (Multi-stage Random Sampling) that was chosen for 389 people. The sample size was determined according to Yamane's method (Taro Yamane). At a confidence level of not less than 95%, with tolerances not exceeding 5%, 14,341 people were found. Of the 135 males, or 34.7%, and 254 females, or 65.3%, the students at Thamwittaya Foundation School were 110, or 28.3%, as shown in Table 5.10, and the age of the students who responded the most was 14 years old, or 54.2%, as shown in Table 3 -5.

Table 4: The Number of School Students who responded to the Needs Questionnaire Needed to Develop a Project-Based Curriculum of Excellence for Islamic Private Secondary School Students. Yala Province

School	Number (persons)	percent
School of Higher Science	71	18.3
Tarbia Tulvantan Foundation School	65	16.7
Thamwittaya Foundation School	110	28.3
Sri Farida Baru Wittaya School	71	18.3
Islamiyah School	72	18.5

Table 5: Age of Students who responded to the Needs Questionnaire Needed to Develop a Project-Based Curriculum of Excellence for Learning Management among Students in Islamic Private Secondary Schools. Yala Province

Age	Number (persons)	percent
12 years	15	3.8
13 years	87	22.4
14 years	211	54.2
15 years	73	18.8
16 years	2	0.6
17 years	1	0.3

Table 6: Grade level Students who responded to the Needs Questionnaire Needed to Develop a Project-Based Curriculum of Excellence for learning Management among Students in Islamic Private Secondary Schools. Yala Province

class	Number (persons)	percent
Secondary Education Year 1	61	15.7
Secondary Education Year 2	67	17.2
Secondary Education Year 3	261	67.1

The results of the analysis of the average score of the factors of learners' attitude towards the decision to pursue higher secondary education indicate the need for the development of a curriculum of excellence with project-based learning as a base for learning management for secondary school students in Yala Province for students classified by actual condition. The need analysis results found that the selected curriculum was in line with the 21st-century learning skills, interests, and likes of the course by the students. Innovations can be created by students to generate extra income during their studies. The study plan can be selected or decided on by oneself. Passion for science can be used, creativity can be employed logically, decisions can be made courageously, and assertiveness in thinking can be exhibited. A passion for research can be demonstrated. Seeking and analyzing can be done. Possession of skills and aptitude in the course learned can be achieved. Laboratory use for scientific skills can be exercised. The condition should be moderate to high, which may be because of the learning management process of the teaching system that does not meet the needs of the learners, as shown in the Table. 7

Table 7

The average score of learners' attitudes towards students' decision to pursue higher secondary education of the need to develop a curriculum of excellence with project-based learning for the learning management of students in Islamic private secondary schools is analyzed. The learning management of students in Islamic private secondary schools in Yala Province by actual condition should be classified. The results of the need analysis are necessary

Attitude factors	Realistic conditions			The condition should be.		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. Cumulative grade point average in junior high school	2.93	1.09	moderate	3.67	0.85	high
2. The need to learn basic subjects that can advance higher education.	3.42	1.21	moderate	3.95	0.89	high
3. The selected curriculum is in line with the learning skills of the 21 century.	2.46	1.33	low	3.71	0.89	high
4. Have an interest and like the course learned.	1.85	1.00	low	3.76	0.95	high
5. Students can create innovations to generate additional income during their studies.	1.30	0.57	low	3.46	1.03	moderate
6. Select/decide the study plan by yourself.	2.18	1.20	low	3.73	0.98	high
7. Have a preference for science and use creativity logically.	2.25	1.06	low	3.76	1.04	high
8. Have the courage to make decisions and be assertive in thinking	1.80	1.11	low	3.48	1.02	moderate

9. Have a passion for research. Seek and analyze	1.60	0.74	low	3.62	0.97	high
10. Possession of skills and aptitudes in the course learned.	1.93	1.01	low	3.59	0.92	high
11. Having scientific skills for laboratory use	1.74	1.04	low	3.67	1.03	high
combine	2.13	1.03	low	3.67	0.96	high

Table 8

Effect of Students' Family Factor Average Score Analysis on Decision Making for High School Education Needs Needed to Develop Project-Based Learning Excellence Curriculum for Learning Management of Students in Islamic Private Secondary Schools Yala Province for students classified by actual condition the condition should be and the results of the need analysis are necessary.

Family factors	Realistic conditions			The condition should be.		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. Parents see that they have the opportunity to pursue higher education.	2.44	0.89	low	3.94	0.91	high
2. Parents' level of education influences their decision to pursue further education.	2.35	0.97	low	3.58	1.08	high
3. Parents consider that the cost of studying this course is appropriate and have the ability to pay tuition fees until the end.	3.33	1.13	moderate	3.67	0.99	high
4. Parents have a stable career with enough income to support the family.	2.85	1.04	moderate	3.55	0.96	high
5. Parents expect and encourage them to continue this course.	3.27	0.90	moderate	3.86	1.01	high
combine	2.34	0.99	low	3.67	0.99	high

The decision to pursue high school education of the need to develop a curriculum of excellence through project-based learning is influenced by the average scores on students' family factor analysis. It was found that the actual conditions were moderate-low, but the possible outcomes should be high. When analyzing the average score of social factors, it is evident that environmental factors, patriotism, religion, and king are involved, as well as the attributes of discipline, desire to learn, and self-sufficiency. The commitment to work, love of Thainess, public spirit, and good attitude towards science and mathematics are also significant factors. The average result of the high school education decision aligns with Table 7-18.

Table 9

Effect of Students' Social Factor Average Score Analysis on Students' Decision to Pursue High School Education Needs Needed to Develop a Project-Based Learning Excellence Curriculum for Learning Management of Students in Islamic Private Secondary Schools Yala Province for students classified by actual condition the condition should be and the results of the need analysis are necessary.

Social factors	Realistic conditions			The condition should be.		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. Parents are advised to study this course.	2.35	0.97	low	3.82	1.01	high
2. Relatives give advice and recommend them to study this course.	2.71	1.20	low	3.57	1.10	high
3. The teacher advises and recommends that you continue this course.	1.32	0.60	low	3.71	1.09	high
4. A friend advises and recommends that you choose to study this course.	2.18	1.20	low	3.65	1.01	high
5. Most friends choose this course.	3.67	0.81	high	3.78	1.11	high
6. A friend persuaded me to take this course.	3.22	0.91	moderate	3.43	1.08	moderate
7. I decided to study in this field because I wanted it to be accepted by parents and relatives.	2.35	0.97	low	3.52	1.02	high
8. The decision to study in this course is because you want it to be accepted by teachers.	2.93	1.09	moderate	3.31	1.13	moderate
combine	2.65	0.97	moderate	3.62	1.05	high

Table 10

Effect of Students' Average Environmental Factors Analysis on Students' Decision to Pursue High School Education Needs to Develop Project-Based Curriculum of Excellence for Learning Management of Students in Islamic Private Secondary Schools Yala Province for students classified by actual condition the condition should be and the results of the need analysis are necessary.

Environmental factors	Realistic conditions			The condition should be.		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. The school is reputable, well-known and accepted by society.	3.42	1.21	moderate	3.80	0.95	high
2. Most graduates can go on to prestigious institutions.	2.46	1.33	low	3.94	0.96	high
3. The school has well-known educational personnel who are accepted by society.	1.87	1.03	low	3.71	0.94	high
4. Educational institutions encourage students to apply their knowledge to create academic works to compete in various departments.	1.30	0.57	low	3.89	0.91	high
5. The school provides advice, supervision, assistance and consultation services on academic standards.	1.87	1.05	low	3.81	0.94	high
6. The school provides a shady atmosphere and environment. Beautiful and appropriate	1.30	0.55	low	3.78	0.98	high

7. The school is located in an environment free from air pollution and disturbances.	2.18	1.20	low	3.64	0.95	high
8. Transportation to the school is convenient and safe.	2.25	1.06	low	3.84	0.93	high
9. The school has libraries, academic centers, textbooks, and documents that are sufficient to meet the needs of students.	1.34	0.66	low	3.71	0.98	high
10. The school is ready for the building. Assembly building, classroom Laboratory and special rooms and modern school supplies	2.18	1.20	low	3.80	1.05	high
11. Educational institutions ranked at the provincial or regional or national level.	2.25	1.06	low	3.64	0.94	high
12. The school supports modern teaching and learning, such as the use of digital media in teaching and learning.	1.59	0.79	low	3.71	1.03	high
13. The school has a project to collaborate with external agencies.	1.98	1.07	low	3.75	0.97	high
combine	1.83	0.93	low	3.75	0.97	high

Table 11

Analysis of the Patriotic Religion and King average score of desirable characteristics of students who graduated from the Core Curriculum B.E. 2551 (2008) and revised in 2017 to study the need to develop a project-based curriculum of excellence for Islamic private secondary school students. Yala Province for students classified by actual condition the condition should be and the results of the need analysis are necessary.

Patriotism, religion, king.	Realistic conditions			The condition should be.		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. Students stand upright and respect the national flag every time they hear the national anthem.	2.25	1.06	low	3.72	1.11	high
2. Be harmonious and able to work well with people around you.	2.93	1.09	moderate	3.99	0.89	high
3. Participate in religious activities that they profess.	3.42	1.21	moderate	4.29	0.88	high
4. Practice according to the principles of one's religion.	2.46	1.33	low	4.34	0.88	high
5. Participate in and participate in activities related to the monarchy.	1.85	1.00	low	3.58	1.10	high
combine	2.29	1.06	low	3.89	0.98	high

Table 12

Average Honesty Score Analysis Integrity of the desirable characteristics of students who have graduated according to the Core Curriculum 2008, revised 2017 in the study of the need to develop a curriculum of excellence with project-based learning as a base for the learning management of secondary school students, private Islamic schools. Yala Province for students classified by actual condition the condition should be and the results of the need analysis are necessary.

Honesty and Integrity	Realistic conditions			The condition should be.		
	\bar{x}	S.D	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. Conduct oneself with regard to accuracy. Shame and fear of wrongdoing.	1.31	0.59	low	4.16	0.93	high
2. Fulfill your promises	2.18	1.20	low	4.03	0.91	high
3. Students can discern what is right and what is wrong.	2.25	1.06	low	4.25	0.89	high
combine	2.33	1.07	low	4.03	0.95	high

Table 13

Analysis of the average score on the discipline of desirable characteristics of students who graduated according to the Core Curriculum B.E. 2551 (2008) and revised in 2017 to study the need to develop a project-based curriculum of excellence for learning management among students in Islamic private secondary schools. Yala Province for students classified by actual condition the condition should be and the results of the need analysis are necessary.

Discipline	Realistic conditions			The condition should be.		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. Dress according to school regulations	1.80	1.11	low	4.39	0.79	high
2. Responsible for performing assigned tasks	1.59	0.73	low	4.09	0.92	high
3. Punctuality and responsibility for oneself and society	1.93	1.01	low	3.98	0.95	high
4. Comply with the agreement. It does not violate the rights of others.	3.27	0.90	moderate	4.13	0.95	high
combine	2.12	1.00	low	4.08	0.93	high

Table 14

Analysis of the average score on learning curiosity of desirable characteristics of students who graduated according to the Core Curriculum B.E. 2551 (2008) and revised in 2017 to study the need to develop a project-based curriculum of excellence for Islamic private secondary school students. Yala Province for students classified by actual condition the condition should be and the results of the need analysis are necessary.

Curiosity to learn	Realistic conditions			The condition should be.		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. Pay attention to studying regularly in class.	2.35	0.97	low	3.98	0.88	high
2. Participate in additional learning activities in addition to learning and know how to use media appropriately.	2.71	1.20	moderate	3.94	0.90	high

3. Diligent in seeking additional knowledge in addition to studying and knowing how to use media appropriately.	1.32	0.61	low	3.84	0.93	high
4. Exchange learning in various ways and apply it in daily life.	2.18	1.20	low	3.96	0.90	high
combine	2.17	0.99	low	4.06	0.91	high

Table 15

Analysis of the average score on self-sufficiency of the desirable characteristics of students who graduated from the Core Curriculum B.E. 2551 (2008) and revised in 2017 to study the need to develop a project-based curriculum of excellence for Islamic private secondary school students. Yala Province for students classified by actual condition the condition should be and the results of the need analysis are necessary.

The side is self-sufficient.	Realistic conditions			The condition should be.		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. Use their own and collective resources economically. Cost-effective and well maintained.	3.67	0.81	moderate	4.05	0.86	high
2. Use money economically and think before spending money on what you want every time.	3.22	0.91	moderate	4.01	0.89	high
3. Turn off the water Always turn off the lights. After use	2.35	0.97	low	4.15	0.88	high
4. Do not take advantage of others and do not cause trouble to others, always forgive when others make mistakes.	2.93	1.09	moderate	4.14	0.94	high
combine	2.57	0.97	moderate	4.03	0.91	high

Table 16

Analysis of average performance score on commitment to the desirable characteristics of students who have graduated according to the Core Curriculum B.E. 2008, revised 2017 in the study of the need to develop a curriculum of excellence with project-based learning for the learning management of secondary school students, Islamic private schools. Yala Province for students classified by actual condition the condition should be, and the results of the need analysis are necessary.

Commitment to work	Realistic conditions			The condition should be.		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. Pay attention to the assigned tasks and complete the tasks on time.	3.42	1.21	moderate	3.94	0.94	high
2. Diligent and patient to solve problems and obstacles in work.	2.46	1.33	low	3.95	0.89	high
3. Know how to divide work, divide duties and work within their own group.	1.87	1.03	low	4.07	0.88	high
combine	2.56	1.01	moderate	4.02	0.90	high

Table 17

Analysis of average scores on Thai love of the desirable characteristics of students who graduated according to the Core Curriculum B.E. 2551 (2008) revised in 2017 to study the need to develop a project-based learning excellence curriculum for learning management among students in Islamic private secondary schools. Yala Province for students classified by actual condition The condition should be and the results of the need analysis are necessary.

Love Thainess	Realistic conditions			The condition should be.		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. Use Thai language to communicate properly and appropriately.	1.30	0.56	low	3.94	0.92	high
2. Participate in the inheritance and conservation of Thai wisdom.	1.87	1.04	low	3.70	0.98	high
3. Thai dress and manners Be grateful to the benefactor.	1.29	0.53	low	3.88	0.92	high
combine	2.35	0.97	low	3.98	0.91	high

Table 18

Analysis of the average score on the public spirit of desirable characteristics of students who graduated from the Core Curriculum B.E. 2551 (2008) and revised in 2017 to study the need to develop a project-based curriculum of excellence for learning management among students in Islamic private secondary schools. Yala Province for students classified by actual condition the condition should be and the results of the need analysis are necessary.

Public Mind	Realistic conditions			The condition should be.		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. Help parents Parents and teachers work willingly.	2.18	1.20	low	4.14	0.94	high
2. Share things, solve problems, or create happiness for others.	2.25	1.06	low	4.09	0.94	high
3. Take care and maintain the public domain and environment willingly.	1.34	0.66	low	4.07	0.92	high
4. Participate in activities that are beneficial to the school. Community & Society	2.18	1.20	low	3.95	0.94	high
5. Help friends and others when they suffer. According to strength and ability without expecting anything in return.	2.25	1.06	low	4.14	0.90	high
Combine	1.95	0.94	low	4.00	0.92	high

Table 19

Analysis of average scores on positive attitude towards science and mathematics of desirable characteristics of students who graduated from the Core Curriculum B.E. 2551 (2008) and revised in 2017 to study the need to develop a project-based curriculum of excellence for Islamic private secondary school students. Yala Province for students classified by actual condition the condition should be and the results of the need analysis are necessary.

Public Mind	Realistic conditions			The condition should be.		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. Science and mathematics are useful subjects for the advancement of new technologies in modern times.	1.59	0.79	low	4.19	0.87	high
2. The knowledge gained from studying science and mathematics can be applied in daily life.	1.98	1.07	low	4.04	0.94	high
combine	1.93	0.96	low	4.02	0.92	high

CONCLUSION

A study of needs in developing an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for learning management of secondary school students at a private Islamic school in Yala Province was conducted. 41 teachers and 389 students, all of whom were from the Yala province, were questioned. The data regarding the traits they wanted their graduating students to have was questioned by the teachers, along with information about projects and activities to develop an excellent curriculum with project-based learning.

For high school students, asking for information about students' decisions to continue their education at the high school level was combined with information on the desired characteristics of students who graduate according to the 2008 core curriculum, revised in 2017.

The results of the study are summarized as follows: The need for the development of an excellent curriculum with project-based learning for the learning management of secondary school students in private Islamic schools in Yala Province was indicated by the results of the study.

The average score obtained from asking teachers in a study of the needs needed to develop an excellent curriculum with project-based learning was high in both the actual context and the expected condition.

But, on the other hand, when inquiring about students' information, it was found that the average score of students who answered the questionnaire about actual conditions would be at a moderate to low level, despite the condition should be at a high level.

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